

SCANDAL AS AN EFFECTIVE MARKETING TOOL**Valishvili Tea,***Akaki Tsereteli State University, Associate Professor***Genelidze Lia***Akaki Tsereteli State University, Visiting Teacher***Abstract**

In modern marketing, consumer attention has become one of the most valuable assets. In an environment where information spreads at an unprecedented pace, brands are constantly seeking ways to capture attention and generate buzz around their products. By attracting emotional reactions and public attention, scandal has emerged as a powerful yet controversial marketing tool. The growing interest in this topic over the past decade is linked to the rapid global dissemination of information through social media platforms.

The study analyzes the reasons and outcomes behind the use of scandal in advertising and examines key approaches to provocative marketing strategies through both international and Georgian brand case studies. It identifies the advantages and risks of such campaigns, also highlighting key factors influencing public perception. Based on a quantitative survey, the study presents Georgian consumers' attitudes toward scandalous advertising. The findings underline the importance of careful risk assessment when using provocative campaigns. The findings show that while such campaigns can effectively boost brand awareness, they often trigger negative emotions that may damage a brand's reputation. Taking these insights into account can help local companies evaluate the potential use of scandal as a marketing tool more wisely and apply it more strategically, minimizing the associated reputational risks. The study underscores the importance of aligning provocative marketing strategies with ethical standards and audience expectations.

Keywords: Provocative marketing, Viral effect, Scandal in advertising, Modern Tools of Marketing Communication

One of the most valuable currencies in modern marketing is consumer attention. In a world where information spreads at an incredible speed, the advertising industry stands at a crossroads between traditional and innovative methods of promoting brands. Amid intense competition, market saturation, and informational noise, companies face the need to find new ways to attract target audiences. The most effective way to capture attention is by generating buzz around a brand, which triggers emotional responses and enhances brand awareness. In this context, scandal becomes a strategic marketing tool. Interest in this subject has increased significantly over the last decade, driven in part by the global spread of information through social media platforms. Studying such advertising strategies is crucial for marketers, who need to understand the risks and opportunities of using scandal in marketing campaigns.

Scandal, as a public phenomenon, consistently attracts the attention of both the media and society. The term "scandal" originates from the Latin "scandalum" and refers to an event that causes public outrage and ethical concern. In marketing, a scandal is usually considered a component of provocative marketing, an approach that seeks to attract the audience's attention by ignoring norms and/or by presenting emotionally charged content. This approach is based on the idea that provocation helps brands quickly gain visibility and acts as a trigger for public discussion across the media and especially in social networks. According to researchers, a scandal can be a powerful tool for increasing brand awareness and creating memorable advertising campaigns. Based on their findings, scandal triggers an "emotional engagement effect", when the audience remembers not only the brand itself, but also the emotions associated with it, which allows the brand

to embed deeper into the consumer's mind. However, the perception of a scandal depends on the target audience and their expectations. Therefore, there is a significant risk that such an approach may harm the brand's reputation and lead to a decrease in customer loyalty.

Analyzing scandals within a marketing context allows us to understand how they can be used to increase brand awareness or enhance consumer engagement. Many brands intentionally use scandals in their marketing strategy to create ongoing public discussion. However, it's important that scandal-based campaigns are carefully planned and executed to prevent potential harm to the brand's long-term reputation. Despite their growing popularity, this approach raises numerous concerns. First, there is the ethical aspect: can the use of scandal in advertising be justified if it contradicts public norms and expectations? Second, we need to consider the long-term impact of such an approach on the brand's image. A scandal can temporarily boost popularity, but it may also damage reputation if consumers view it as immoral or manipulative. Third, the impact of such campaigns on consumers is often emotional, requiring careful analysis in terms of psychology and consumer behavior. In this context, it is sufficient to recall examples of the controversial campaigns of "BALENCIAGA" and the opening ceremony of the Paris Olympics. These cases highlight that the audience's reactions to scandalous campaigns can vary widely due to social, cultural, and age differences. While younger audiences may view them as creative and bold, older individuals might find them offensive or aggressive. Furthermore, it is essential to recognize the role of the social context in a campaign. Time and place play a critical role in how advertising messages

are received; what is considered innovative in one society may lead to criticism and backlash in another. In a globalized world, the use of scandal in advertising becomes particularly complex, as the same campaign may be interpreted in vastly different ways across countries and cultures.

There are numerous examples of scandalous campaigns, but we would like to draw attention specifically to those initiated by Georgian brands. The first notable case is “Barambo” and its campaign titled “Children, don't trust your parents”. The campaign caused outrage among parents and widespread public discussion precisely because of this call. The creative team quickly explained, noting that they were counting on the scandal, as their goal was to increase awareness in a short period of time, which was the only way to achieve it. While confectionery company Barambo’s campaign can be considered successful, since it did not significantly damage the brand’s image, in fact increased brand awareness, the same cannot be said for the second example. This case involves “GPI Holding” and its promotional campaign titled “Careful, there’s a woman in the car mirror.” Intended as a humorous, Women’s Day-themed advertisement, the campaign was perceived by a segment of the female audience as offensive and discriminatory. The public reaction was swift and critical, with users expressing outrage across social media by posting comments. The backlash highlighted how a scandalous campaign, if poorly executed or culturally insensitive, can severely damage a brand’s reputation.

Based on the above information, we can generalize several criteria that can be outlined for developing ethical marketing campaigns:

- Human rights and responsibility. Scandalous marketing, while emotionally powerful, must be conducted with a strong sense of social responsibility. It’s essential for brands to consider human rights issues and to avoid discriminatory or offensive language.
- Monitoring public reactions. A key principle of ethical marketing is the continuous evaluation of public response. It is essential to assess how a campaign might affect the wider audience, as brand reputation can suffer serious consequences if the campaign fails to align with consumer values and standards.
- Acknowledgment and timely apology. If a scandalous campaign escalates into a crisis, brands must act quickly and communicate effectively. Issuing a public apology and taking visible steps to correct mistakes becomes essential to prevent the brand from losing customer trust.

The use of scandal in marketing holds both advantages and disadvantages. On the positive side, scandalous events or statements tend to receive extensive media coverage, resulting in free publicity. They also promote rapid information dissemination, helping brands secure top positions in search engines, social networks, and news. Moreover, emotionally charged content is more memorable, making scandals an effective tool for increasing brand awareness. However, there are also serious drawbacks. A scandal may damage a company’s image and alienate loyal customers, posing serious reputational risks. It can lead to a loss of

consumer trust, as customers may reject a brand’s products or services in response to its actions. Additionally, scandalous statements or behavior may result in legal consequences, including regulatory scrutiny or lawsuits.

To evaluate the effectiveness of scandal as a marketing tool and its impact on consumer behavior, we conducted an online, anonymous survey using a questionnaire. In total, 200 respondents participated in the survey, and all responses were analyzed collectively. The target audience consisted of individuals aged 18 to 55. The questionnaire was specifically designed for this research purpose and was categorized into five thematic sections: respondent’s demographic information, attention and awareness, emotional response and behavior, and long-term impact.

Based on the content analysis and synthesis of scientific works and publications, the following hypotheses were formulated:

- H1.Scandalous marketing campaigns attract more consumer attention than traditional marketing strategies.
- H2.The use of scandal in marketing causes both positive and negative emotions, which affect consumer behavior in various ways.
- H3.Consumers’ age and social status affect their attitude towards scandalous marketing campaigns.
- H4.Scandal, as a marketing tool, is more effective in social media platforms than in traditional media.
- H5.Consumers consider scandalous campaigns as a strategy that is temporarily effective, but is associated with long-term reputational risk.

Among the respondents, 35% are 18-24 years old, 28% 25-34 years old, 18% 35-44 years old, and 19% are over 45 years old. As the data indicates, the majority of respondents are representatives of the youth age group, since the younger audience is more active on social media platforms, where the survey was conducted. In response to the question, “To what extent do scandalous advertising campaigns capture your attention?”, approximately 90% of respondents indicate that such campaigns do attract their attention. 55% of respondents state that scandalous campaigns draw their attention more than traditional ones, while 23% believe that both types of campaigns are equally attention-grabbing. Only 22% state that they find traditional advertising more attention-worthy. When asked, “What kind of emotions do you have towards scandalous advertising campaigns?”, more than half of the respondents express positive emotions, whereas 28% express negative emotional reactions toward such content. To the question, “Do you think scandalous campaigns influence consumer behavior?”, 38% responded yes, positively; 20% answered yes, but negatively; while 31% believe that they do not have influence.

The majority of respondents (74%) believe that scandalous campaigns are more appealing to younger audiences. Furthermore, 82% think that such campaigns are more effective on social media platforms. While some respondents noted the risk of potential reputational damage, a large majority (46%) consider scandalous marketing to be effective in the long term.

Also, 46% believe that the impact of scandal-based campaigns is more temporary than lasting.

Based on the survey outcomes, we can draw the following conclusions:

- Hypotheses H1, H3, H4, and H5 were confirmed, while hypothesis H2 was partially confirmed.
- Scandalous campaigns are more popular among younger audiences, as they attract more attention on social media platforms.
- Social media is considered an effective platform for performing scandalous campaigns.
- Some respondents still believe that scandalous campaigns may harm a brand's reputation, which highlights the necessity for careful planning and monitoring of such strategies.

In conclusion, the use of scandal as a marketing tool can be both effective and risky. Provocative campaigns capture public attention, but they also pose potential threats to the brand's reputation and raise ethical concerns. Finally, we can conclude that a scandal has a dual effect: it may effectively draw attention to a brand and increase awareness, yet at the same time, it can damage the brand's reputation and alienate parts of the audience. The successful use of scandal in marketing requires a deep understanding of the target audience and a crafted strategy to ensure not only attention but also long-term support of the brand's positive perception. It's essential to respect ethical boundaries, ensuring content remains appropriate and non-discriminatory. Further, having a crisis communication plan and

monitoring audience reactions can help manage potential backlash. Scandal should only be used when it aligns with the brand's values and long-term goals, and when the advantages outweigh the risks.

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